

A NEW THERMOFORMING CFRP BY PENETATING PHENOL-MODIFIED PP INTO CF MAT

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1 Introduction

For the high-speed production of big car parts, *e.g.*, fender, the injection molding of plastics cannot overcome the press forming of steel plates. Thermoforming of plastics sheet, *e.g.*, stamping and vacuum forming, would lead to the faster production. It will also save the mold cost and render more flexibility of parts design both in shape and size. We propose here a new thermoforming CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastics) sheet. The CFRP sheet was prepared by press-penetrating a high-flow polypropylene (PP) modified with phenol resin into CF mat. The CFRP showed remarkably high performance; much higher modulus and toughness than the conventional CFRP by simple melt-mixing of PP with CF.

2 Experimental

To prepare a high-flow PP modified with phenol, an injection-grade PP was melt-mixed with phenol resin and organic peroxide (DCP: dicumyl peroxide) in twin-screw extruder at 200°C. The fluidity was evaluated in terms of the melt index (MI) at 200°C. The modified PP (donated as PP-Ph) was subjected to the uniaxial tensile test. PP-Ph was melt-pressed to a thin sheet (0.1 mm thick). Two sheets sandwiched a CF mat and melt-pressed at 200°C for 5 min to penetrate the PP-Ph as shown in Fig. 1. The CF mat is a non-woven fabric type, consisting of short carbon fibers of 7 μm diameter and 7 mm length. The press-penetrated PP-Ph/CF composite

Fig. 1 Preparation of PP/CF composite by press-penetration

sheets were piled up and then melt-pressed to a thick (1 mm) plate. Further, a neat PP sheet was sandwiched by two thin CFRP sheets and melt-pressed to prepare a laminated 3 layer sample (CFRP/PP/CFRP; see Fig.4). As a control sample, PP and short CF were melt-mixed in the twin screw extruder at 200°C.

3. Results and Discussion

The fluidity was successfully increased by increasing DCP content, implying the chain scission (decrease in molecular weight). Surprisingly, the elongation at break did not decrease but increased with increasing the fluidity, as shown in Fig. 2. For the CFRP, we used a PP-Ph of MI=100 g/10min. It was shown to be 0.35 wt% Ph-grafted by FTIR analysis after solvent (acetone) extraction.

Fig. 2 Super ductile PP-Ph with excellent fluidity (large MI)

As shown in Fig. 3, in the CFRP plate, PP-Ph well penetrated and wetted the carbon fibers. The original fiber length remained without breaking down during the processing and the fibers were dispersed at random in xy-plane. Adhesive strength between GF and PP-Ph was evaluated by a single fiber breaking method (Fig. 4) to be much higher than the GF/PP system.

In the conventional CFRP prepared by simple melt-blending, the rigidity increased by the incorporation of CF but the toughness was sacrificed as shown in Fig. 5. By contrast, both the rigidity and the toughness dramatically increased in the melt-penetrated CFRP.

Fig. 3 SEM of press-penetrated composites.

Fig. 4 Interfacial adhesive strength, evaluated by a single fiber breaking method

In Table I, the flexural properties are compared with other materials, such as metals and prepreg-type CFRP. The specific rigidity and strength are several times higher than steel. It would lead to a remarkable weight reduction of cars.

Fig. 5 Toughness and rigidity of CFRP

Fig. 6 shows that the flexural strength of CFRP is not sacrificed so much by inserting the neat PP sheet. It suggests that the strength above 200 MPa can be achieved by incorporating 15 wt% CF. Thus, one can reduce the loading amount of expensive CF.

Fig. 6 Strength of CFRP/PP/CFRP sandwich composite. Thickness of neat PP sheet was varied.

Table 1. Flexural properties CFRP, compared with other materials.

	Flex. Modulus, E (GPa)	Flex. Strength, σ (MPa)	Density, ρ (g/ml)	Specific rigidity ($\sqrt[3]{E/\rho}$)	Specific strength ($\sqrt{\sigma/\rho}$)
Steel	200	420	7.8	0.75 (×1)	2.6 (×1)
Aluminum	71	160	2.7	1.5 (×2.1)	4.7 (×1.8)
Magnesium	45	370	1.8	2.0 (×2.6)	11 (×4.1)
Prepreg CFRP Epoxy (V_f 60%)	50	700	1.5	2.5 (×3.3)	18 (×6.7)
Press-penetrated PP-CFRP	14.5	300	1.1	2.3 (×3.0)	16 (×6.2)

By stamping the CFRP, a (ca. 500 mm x 400 mm x 2 mm) sheet with many sinks (drawings) was nicely fabricated as a model for big car parts (Fig, 7).

500 mm x 400 mm

Fig.7. Photo of a model for car parts fabricated by stamping.

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